

Towards the effective inclusion of Roma history and culture in the Spanish education system (2025-2030)

Mariana Santiago-Vargas

1. Summary

Spain has an advanced regulatory framework that explicitly recognises the history and culture of the Roma people in the education system: Ley Orgánica 3/2020, de 29 de diciembre, por la que se modifica la Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de mayo, de Educación (LOMLOE)¹, the National Strategy for Equality, Inclusion and Participation of the Roma Population 2021 – 2030², Law 15/2022 on equal treatment and non-discrimination³ and Law 20/2022 on Democratic Memory⁴. However, these mandates have barely translated into structural changes in curricula, textbooks, teacher education and school culture, thus maintaining a gap between the law and the reality of classrooms.

Some relevant current data on the Roma population: Almost 70 % of the Roma population lives in moderate or severe social exclusion, compared to 18.4 % of the overall population¹ (See Figure 1).

The early school-leaving rate among Roma students reaches 62.8 %, compared to 4 % among the general student population²⁹ (See Figure 1).

ECRI notes that a very significant proportion of Roma students are educated in highly segregated schools and recommends structural and sustained measures against segregation¹⁵.

Figure 1. Social exclusion, early school-leaving and school segregation affecting Roma students in Spain

Source: Own elaboration.

Proposal

It is proposed that the Ministry of Education, Vocational Training and Sports launch a State – Autonomous Communities Programme 2025 – 2030 for the effective inclusion of Roma history and culture, structured around three axes (see Figure 2):

- 1 Curriculum, textbooks and assessment. Approval, within the Sectoral Conference on Education, of a Common Framework for the Curricular Inclusion of the Roma People, with core knowledge and assessment criteria in primary and lower secondary education (ESO), consistent with LOMLOE¹, the Royal Decrees on minimum teaching requirements^{9,10} and Law 20/2022⁴.
- 2 Teacher training: mandatory inclusion of content on Roma history and Mandatory teacher education. Inclusion of modules on Roma history and culture, antigypsyism and culturally relevant pedagogy in initial and in-service teacher education, aligned with multicultural education and culturally responsive teaching frameworks^{16,17}.
- 3 Resources, pilot schools and an Excellence Seal. Development of a national package of open educational resources (including gamified proposals, materials designed according to Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and augmented and virtual reality experiences) and a network of pilot schools awarded a Seal of Excellence in Roma Curricular Inclusion, with external support and evaluation, generating scalable models of good practice^{11,18,27,28}.

Source: Own elaboration.

This is an agenda with a moderate additional cost, combinable with ordinary education budgets and European funds (ESF+, ERDF, Erasmus+). It responds to regulatory commitments already undertaken^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7} and to demands both from the Roma associative movement^{13,14,21,22} and from the scientific community specialised in inclusive and intercultural education and in antigypsyism^{12,18,19,23,24}.

2. Context and policy problem

2.1. Existing regulatory and strategic commitments

Ley Orgánica 3/2020, de 29 de diciembre, por la que se modifica la Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de mayo, de Educación (LOMLOE) establishes that the education system must promote “the study and respect of other cultures, particularly that of the Roma people (...) as well as the recognition and dissemination of the history and culture of ethnic minorities present in our country” (p.17)¹. The National Strategy 2021 – 2030 places real equality, socio-economic inclusion and participation of the Roma population at the centre of state policy, with a specific axis on education and the fight against antigypsyism². Law 15/2022 consolidates the right to equal treatment and non-discrimination in all areas, including education³, and Law 20/2022 on Democratic Memory makes it mandatory to include in study plans the memory of those who suffered persecution or violence, which covers the history of antigypsyism⁴.

Royal Decrees 157/2022 and 217/2022 incorporate cultural diversity and democratic memory as core elements of the curriculum and make specific reference to the Roma people in some core competences in Social Sciences and Values Education in primary and lower secondary education^{9,10}. At the European level, the EU Roma Strategic Framework 2020 – 2030⁵, the Council Recommendation on Roma equality, inclusion and participation⁶ and the Council of Europe Recommendation CM/Rec(2020)27⁷ call for the integration of Roma history, culture and memory into school curricula and teacher education, in line with the vision of inclusion set out in UNESCO’s 2020 GEM Report⁸.

2.2. The gap between the law and classroom realities

Empirical analyses conducted by the Ministry and by university research groups indicate that Roma culture, when it appears at all, is typically represented in a marginal, folklorised or stereotyped manner in most primary and secondary textbooks^{11,12}. The inclusion of more substantive and systematic content depends largely on the discretionary initiative of certain regional authorities, schools or individual teachers, resulting in a highly uneven territorial landscape and a “patchwork” of educational opportunities for Roma students^{12,19,21}.

The VIII FOESSA Report documents very high levels of poverty, precarious employment and residential exclusion among the Roma population, conditions that have a direct impact on educational trajectories.¹⁴ In parallel, ECRI confirms the existence of de facto school segregation affecting Roma students in Spain and calls for structural and sustained measures to address it¹⁵. Scholarly work on ethnic minorities and education systems describes the emergence of “Roma school circuits” and organisational arrangements that reproduce segregating dynamics within and between schools^{19,20,21}. Research focusing on Roma girls and young women identifies specific gendered barriers while also highlighting processes of change and agency among students and their families¹³. In higher education, Roma university students remain an exception, although their presence is associated with a considerable transformative potential in both academic and community spheres²².

At the same time, the curricula of education degrees and master’s programmes largely fail to address Roma history and culture or antigypsyism in a systematic way. Evidence from teacher education programmes on Roma education in other national contexts shows that positive changes occur when training is sustained over time and explicitly linked to curricular reform^{25,26}. In the absence of such training, the implementation of existing curricular provisions depends on individual teacher voluntarism, and low expectations and prejudicial attitudes towards Roma students tend to be reproduced^{13,23}.

The literature on multicultural education, culturally responsive teaching and school inclusion^{16,17,18} converges with research specifically focused on Roma students^{12,19,21,23}: without structural changes in curriculum, teacher education and school organisation, the inclusion of Roma students remains fragile, contingent on isolated and localised initiatives rather than embedded as a robust, system-level policy. There are two main reasons why it is important to include Roma culture and history in the curriculum. The first one is that it motivates Roma children because they feel represented; secondly, non-Roma pupils have the opportunity to familiarize themselves with another culture, which results in more acceptance and closeness, breaking down existing prejudices.

3. Policy options considered

The following section contains three policy options to tackle the issue of the lack of inclusion and representation of Roma history and culture, which are discussed based on their advantages and disadvantages in relation to their political, economic, societal, technological, ecological and legal aspects (Figure 3).

Option 0. Continuation of the status quo

Maintain the current regulatory framework (LOMLOE¹, National Strategy², Laws 15/2022³ and 20/2022⁴) and existing initiatives (guidance materials¹¹, ad hoc projects) without additional measures.

Advantage: very low immediate political and budgetary cost.

Risks: consolidates the gap between policy discourse and classroom reality^{11,12}; keeps inclusion symbolic and voluntaristic, with sharp territorial inequalities^{19,21}; does not adequately respond to European recommendations or to the demands of the Roma movement and the scientific community^{5,6,7,12,18,23,24}.

Option 1. Symbolic measures and one-off actions

Strengthen awareness-raising campaigns, commemorative events, some additional materials and isolated pilot projects (for example linked to Roma commemorative dates)².

Advantages: improves symbolic visibility of the Roma people and generates inspiring experiences in some schools.

Risks: limited and fragmented impact, dependent on school-level willingness; does not change curriculum, assessment or teacher education, as comparative experience shows^{8,23,24}; difficult to monitor and to align with European follow-up indicators^{5,6,8}.

Option 2. State-Autonomous Communities Programme 2025-2030

Design and implement a programme that connects curriculum, textbooks, teacher education, resources, incentives and monitoring indicators, in line with National Strategy² and equality³ and memory⁴ laws into system-level change; allows 2030 targets and comparable indicators to be set, with accountability to national and European institutions^{5,6,8}; responds to demands from the Roma movement and the scientific community^{12, 18, 21, 22, 24}; strengthens Spain's leadership in equality, democratic memory and the fight against antigypsyism^{5,6,7,8}.

Risks: requires close coordination with regional authorities and active change management in schools; demands a clear political narrative to avoid perceptions of “curricular overload” among teachers.

Figure 3: Education System Improvement Options

Source: Napkin.

Based on structural impact, moderate additional cost and alignment with European and national commitments, the most effective and coherent option is Option 2- State-Autonomous Communities Programme 2025 – 2030.

4. Recommendation: Option 2 - State-Autonomous Communities Programme 2025-2030

Overall objective

Move from a generic mention of the Roma people in legislation^{1,2,3,4} to their effective, assessable and visible inclusion in curriculum, teacher education, resources and school practices, in line with EU frameworks^{5,6}, Council of Europe standards⁷ and UNESCO recommendations⁸.

To clarify how the proposed programme operates in practice, Figure 4 offers a visual map of Roma curricular inclusion, organising the three axes—Curriculum, Textbooks and Assessment; Teacher Education; and Resources and Pilot Schools/Excellence Seal—around a central goal. The diagram highlights the main strands of action under each axis (common framework and

textbook review, initial and in-service teacher education, open and innovative resources, pilot schools network and Excellence Seal) and shows how they converge to support a coherent, system-level approach to Roma curricular inclusion (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Roma curricular inclusion: strategies and initiatives across the three axes

Source: Own elaboration.

Axis 1. Curriculum, textbooks and assessment

- Agree, within the Sectoral Conference on Education, a Common Framework for the Curricular Inclusion of the Roma People, defining core knowledge and assessment criteria on Roma history, culture, persecutions, memory and contributions in primary and lower secondary education (and, where appropriate, upper secondary), consistent with LOMLOE¹, Royal Decrees 157/2022⁹ and 217/2022¹⁰ and Law 20/2022⁴.
- Incorporate explicit references to combating antigypsyism, aligned with European recommendations^{5,6,7}.
- Establish a mechanism for the review of textbooks and materials, with participation from the administration, the scientific community and Roma organisations, to guarantee rigorous, non-stereotyped representation^{11,12,19,21}.
- Define monitoring indicators by region and school stage, integrated into the annual monitoring of the National Strategy² and into reports submitted to the EU⁵ and the Council of Europe⁷.

Axis 2. Initial and in-service teacher education

- Objective: ensure that teachers have the professional competences needed to work on Roma history and culture from a human-rights-based perspective, multicultural education, Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and culturally relevant pedagogy^{16,17,18}.
- Incorporate specific learning outcomes on Roma history and culture, antigypsyism and intercultural education in primary and early childhood education degrees, pedagogy and social education degrees, and in the Master's in

Secondary Teacher Training^{16,17}.

- Integrate these contents as a quality criterion in the accreditation of education degrees.
- Establish, in regional in-service training plans, a priority strand on Roma history and culture and the fight against antigypsyism, with certified pathways that include the use of gamification and emerging technologies (augmented and virtual reality) framed within UDL, in collaboration with Roma experts²², research groups in inclusive education^{12,19,23,24} and teacher training centres and universities^{25,26}.

Axis 3. Resources, pilot schools and an Excellence Seal

- Consolidate a national repository of open educational resources (OER) on Roma history and culture (didactic units, audiovisual materials, whole-school projects), organised by educational stage and subject¹¹.
- Promote innovative resources that bring together historical, gender, child-rights and human-rights perspectives, supported by active methodologies such as project-based learning and gamification, and by emerging technologies (augmented and virtual reality, immersive environments), designed according to UDL principles^{18,27,28}.
- Select, in collaboration with regional authorities, a network of pilot schools that develop whole-school projects on Roma history and culture, with technical support, co-design spaces with families and Roma organisations² and external evaluation with dissemination of results^{9,18}.
- Create a Seal of Excellence in Roma Curricular Inclusion, linked to priority access to innovation calls, additional staff and coordination time, and public recognition.

5. Governance, financing and risk management

5.1. Governance

Governance of the programme will rest on clear political and technical leadership, robust territorial coordination and an inclusive decision-making structure. The State Secretariat for Education (Ministry of Education, Vocational Training and Sports) will assume overall responsibility, with a dedicated unit within the Directorate-General in charge of equity and attention to diversity providing technical direction and day-to-day management. Territorial coordination with the Autonomous Communities will be channelled through the Sectoral Conference on Education, which will serve as the forum for co-design, agreement and follow-up with regional authorities on the Common Curricular Framework, teacher education and the network of pilot schools^{9,10}. In parallel, a State Commission for the Educational Inclusion of the Roma People will be

established as a mixed body bringing together central and regional governments, universities, Roma organisations and individual experts, with decision-making powers in areas of state competence (basic curriculum, Excellence Seal criteria and state programmes). This Commission will have a majority of Roma members (at least 60 – 70 %) and a majority of Roma women, as a positive-action measure to address their historical under-representation in education decision-making, while territorial implementation will continue to be organised through agreements reached within the Sectoral Conference.

5.2. Financing

The proposed agenda entails a moderate additional cost, concentrated on three main areas: the development and updating of curricular materials and digital resources^{11,27}; the design and delivery of specific modules in initial and in-service teacher education^{16,17,25,26}; and the provision of support, evaluation and targeted reinforcements to a limited network of pilot schools^{18,21}. These costs can be covered through a combination of ordinary education budgets of the Ministry and regional authorities, particularly the budget lines dedicated to equity, innovation and teacher education^{1,2,3,4} and European structural and investment funds. In this regard, the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) can be mobilised to support social and educational inclusion initiatives^{5,6}, while the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) can contribute to financing infrastructure and digital resources^{5,6}; in addition, European programmes such as Erasmus+ (cooperation partnerships and innovation alliances) offer further opportunities to fund collaborative projects, capacity-building and the scaling-up of successful practices^{5,6,7}.

5.3. Risks and mitigation

Potential risks associated with the implementation of the programme can be mitigated through a combination of anticipatory design, coherent framing and inclusive governance. Possible reluctance among some regional authorities can be addressed through early co-design, explicit scope for territorial adaptation and a clear linkage between the programme and objectives already included in the National Strategy² and relevant European frameworks^{5,6,7}. Concerns about perceived overload among teachers can be mitigated by embedding the proposed changes into existing frameworks (LOMLOE¹, Universal Design for Learning^{18,27} and school coexistence plans), providing ready-to-use resources that minimise additional preparation time¹¹ and associating the Excellence Seal with protected coordination time and additional staff.

The risk of folklorisation or stigmatising approaches should be countered by ensuring the active participation of Roma experts in curricular design and material review^{12,22}, systematically drawing on intercultural education research^{19,21} and using the Index for Inclusion as a tool to revise school cultures, policies and practices¹⁸. Finally, the danger of political instrumentalisation can be reduced by consistently framing the agenda in terms of educational quality⁸, democratic memory⁴, compliance with European commitments^{5,6,7} and broader social cohesion objectives¹⁴.

6. What is requested from the Cabinet

It is proposed that the Cabinet adopt an explicit political mandate to design and launch, before the end of 2025, the State – Autonomous Communities Programme 2025 – 2030 for the curricular inclusion of Roma history and culture. Within this mandate, the Cabinet should instruct the State Secretariat for Education to draw up, within a period of 6 – 9 months, a comprehensive programme proposal that includes: a Common Framework for Roma Curricular Inclusion, specifying core knowledge and assessment criteria in primary and lower secondary education; a proposal for the inclusion of relevant contents in university education degrees and in in-service teacher education; and the design of a national repository of resources, a network of pilot schools and the associated Excellence Seal.

In addition, the Cabinet should establish a mixed working group, comprising representatives of the Ministry, regional authorities, universities, Roma experts and researchers in the field to co-design the programme and its monitoring indicators, ensuring the effective participation of the Roma associative movement and of the specialised scientific community^{12, 18, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26}. It is further recommended that the Cabinet identify and secure the necessary funding lines, combining ordinary education budgets with ESF+, ERDF and Erasmus+ funds^{5,6,7}, and that it request a progress report in 2027 and an interim evaluation in 2029, in order to facilitate programme adjustment over time and to ensure robust accountability to Parliament, civil society and European institutions^{5,6,8}.

Conclusion

Spain currently has an advanced legal framework (LOMLOE, Law 15/2022, Law 20/2022, national strategies) and a favourable European environment (EU strategic framework and Council of Europe recommendations) to turn the inclusion of Roma history and culture in the curriculum into a central axis of its education, equality and innovation policies. The challenge is no longer normative, but strategic and operational. Spain must move from generic legal references to the concrete presence of Roma history and culture in curricular contents, textbooks, teacher education and innovative school practices. Doing so would not only close the gap between LOMLOE and classroom reality, but would also strengthen Spain's position as a European reference in the fight against antigypsyism, advancing towards truly inclusive education consistent with the democratic principles the education system itself is committed to uphold. This is an agenda with moderate cost and high structural impact, built on existing instruments, which can be implemented gradually up to 2030 and offers the Ministry a clear opportunity for leadership in equality, diversity and educational quality in the European context.

This policy brief was originally drafted in Spanish and translated into English by the author with the assistance of AI-based language tools (ChatGPT, OpenAI) and online dictionaries. The author has carefully reviewed and verified all AI-generated text and remains fully responsible for the content.

Endnotes

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